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TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR AS A SECOND LANGUAGE USING CORPUS-BASED EXAMPLES FOR INTERMEDIATE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Abstract. *The article covers various information about the necessity of teaching intermediate level students corpus-based examples as well as the ways of how to teach them using COCA. Apart from that, the efficiency of corpus-based examples will be given throughout the article.*

Key words: *language skills, corpus-based pedagogy, corpora, COCA, language atmosphere, higher outcomes, grammar of the register, ELLs, L1.*

Introduction. Teaching grammar to intermediate level students is considered to be one of the most vital aspects of language skills to be improved. Normally, intermediate learners have the conception on basic rules of parts of speech, articles, prepositions, the main idea of smaller passages. Besides, they are able to comprehend the instructions given due to their level of language proficiency. To achieve success in terms of levelling up and achieving higher outcomes they need grammar rules. Obviously, not similar to children, adults have grammatical conception of using functions correctly, what is appropriate and what is not appropriate (Moskowitz, 1978, p. 92). Apart from that, Folse (2009) noted that grammar plays basic role in learning the language (p. 1).

Discussion. A number of teachers of English use various methods in order to teach grammar. Green (2018) pointed out that corpus-based pedagogy maintains the learners' awareness on differentiating the language structure in the context. Teachers who are using corpus approach and implementing it into language atmosphere must have the conception of effectively using the corpora (Green, 2018). Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) is regarded as free online corpora including language samples used to develop classroom lessons.

I have chosen the topic **Indefinite pronouns** in order to present corpus-based examples while teaching. Mostly Intermediate learners partially know about indefinite pronouns, particularly *some*, *any*, *no* and their compounds. Morley (2000) defined indefinite pronouns as “an entity whose identity is not specific”.

However, Folse (2009) noted that ELLs have some confusion on using indefinite pronouns (p. 53). Among those pronouns the most commonly used one is **some** and its compounds. The graphs and screenshots below depict a number of examples with **some** and its compounds in the context. With the help of the examples a learner will have understanding on how to use this type of pronoun owing to his or her level. To focus on intermediate level students’ grammatical awareness of indefinite pronouns, the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) can be used. Once I have registered COCA, I logged in with my e-mail address as well as password. Following this, I wrote the word “**SOME**” with capital letters.

When I clicked on “**Find matching strings**” the frequency of the word appeared displaying 1685783.

In order to collect the data about in which sphere this pronoun is used more frequently, I clicked on the button “**Chart**” and it showed that **SPOKEN ENGLISH** is dominant with the usage of this pronoun.

With the help of “**WORD**” search we can get very detailed information about the pronoun “**SOME**”. As above-mentioned this pronoun is mostly used in spoken English whereas academic field shows its rather less usage. Being aware of the frequency of this pronoun in spoken context, students will have the confidence in using it in spoken English.

We can see clusters, related words, concordance lines as well as being distributed into parts of speech with various colours by means of COCA.

Green – adjectives, **blue** – nouns, **yellow** – verbs, **pink** – adverbs. Using either related words or synonyms helps ELLs to be provided with expanded vocabulary and it maintains to deal with the word searching problems while writing and speaking.

<https://www.english-corpora.org/help/changeCorpus.asp>

Apart from that, there are a great many examples available with the pronoun “SOME” in the top of the screen in “CONTEXT”. For example, “*He soon died. I had lost some others, but that was a great friendship and I thought about it a lot*”.

<https://www.english-corpora.org/coca/help/download.asp>

In the following table there are some examples which have been taken from COCA:

№	Pronoun	Related words	Example	The source of examples
1	Some	some	<i>I discuss some of them</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
2	Some	some	<i>Some entrepreneurs are ready to press "SEND"</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
3	Some	somewhere	<i>Jupiter is somewhere between two and twelve Earth masses</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
4	Some	somebody	<i>We must fight! Let somebody else fight.</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
5	Some	somebody	<i>Let me see the purse. Somebody got the jumbo pack.</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
6	Some	somebody	<i>Somebody is now saying it's not just me.</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
7	Some	somewhere	<i>Have I seen this shirt somewhere before?</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
8	Some	somewhere	<i>Knowledge came from somewhere and could influence belief</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
9	Some	some	<i>Some companies are now offering refunds to customers</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
10	Some	some	<i>And we need some more explaining</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org

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Conclusion. Teaching English grammar for those whose L1 is not English has been a challenging practice. Particularly, providing ELLs with learned language patterns while teaching requires to have an understanding of grammar of the register. As it was

previously stated, since indefinite pronouns are considered to be confusing, students should be taught discrepancies between the types of pronouns as well as the usage of them by giving them more examples in the context. By emphasizing indefinite pronouns students whose L1 is not English enhance their writing and speaking skills as it is the requirement for obtaining a language proficiency certificate. Thus, with the help of corpus-based examples, specifically, COCA teachers can effectively teach the topic and provide the students with an authentic texts and articles as well. Or more precisely, COCA is advantageous in terms of increasing students' awareness of any kind of language structure as well as comprehending the discrepancies between and observing various situations coming in the context.

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